

Comparison of the activity of two elastin-like recombinant carriers fused to the antimicrobial peptide indolicidin

Laura Colomina-Alfaro ^a, Paola Sist ^a, Angela Ivask ^c, Brenda Raid ^c, Hanna Ainelo ^c, Abeer Shaalan ^d, Lucy Di Silvio ^d, Ranieri Urbani ^b, Artemis Stamboulis ^e, Antonella Bandiera ^{a,*}

^a Department of Life Sciences, University of Trieste, via Giorgieri, 1, 34127 Trieste, Italy

^b Department of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Trieste, via Giorgieri, 1, 34127 Trieste, Italy

^c Institute of Molecular and Cell Biology, University of Tartu, Riia 23, Tartu, Estonia

^d Centre for Oral, Clinical & Translational Sciences, Faculty of Dentistry, Oral & Craniofacial Sciences, King's College London, London, United Kingdom

^e School of Metallurgy and Materials, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, United Kingdom

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ABSTRACT

Recombinant fusion biotechnology is a powerful tool for producing antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), which can contribute to limiting the number of potentially infectious microorganisms. AMPs are often expressed in fusion with a carrier protein, a strategy that prevents toxic effects on host bacterial cells and protects them from proteolytic degradation. Among the many fusion carriers available, elastin-like polypeptides offer several valuable advantages related to their unique thermo-responsive behavior. The Human Elastin-like Polypeptide was successfully employed to produce a model fusion construct with the indolicidin domain. Recently, an elastin-based variant of this polypeptide was developed, modulating the sequence of the hydrophobic domains, thus enhancing the phase transition properties. Here, a new carrier based on this sequence that was produced, physicochemically characterized, and employed as a fusion partner for the indolicidin is described. This work aims to compare two different elastin-based carriers and their indolicidin fusion derivatives, as well as to determine, based on their properties, which may be the most advantageous carrier for producing antimicrobial domains. This study was focused on the elastin-like polypeptides as a tunable expression platform particularly suitable for producing AMPs and for their integration in biomimetic interfaces that acquire the capacity to inhibit bacterial growth.

1. Introduction

The global threat posed by the emergence and spread of microorganisms that are resistant to available drugs has boosted the interest in antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) as a hopeful alternative to conventional antibiotics. They present a wide-range antimicrobial activity and a low risk of developing rapid resistance [1]. Furthermore, physiologically, they discriminate between pathogen and mutualist microorganisms vital to health. However, there are still numerous issues and limitations to their clinical use, mainly related to the cost of production as well as to the stability and the pharmacokinetic in vivo [2]. Standard chemical synthesis is currently the main route of production for AMPs. Nevertheless, large-scale production is also constrained by the size of the peptides, and some sequences, such as difficult-to-synthesize and cysteine-rich sequences, are challenging to produce, especially due to

hurdles that negatively affect the production yield [3]. Furthermore, there is a greater emphasis on the need for more sustainable procedures with a lower environmental impact, particularly reducing the use of toxic reagents and the generation of hazardous wastes [4].

Peptides are biotic compounds that can be easily obtained by biotechnological recombinant processes, which, due to their flexibility, scalability, and sustainability, are recognized as a promising and greener alternative to conventional chemical synthesis. AMP production in *E. coli* cells is frequently achieved by employing of fusion carriers that mask AMP toxicity towards the host bacterial cells and improve their stability [5]. Although elastin-like polypeptides (ELPs) present several valuable advantages with respect to other fusion carriers, their employment to produce AMPs is still limited [6]. This group of recombinant biopolymers offers the opportunity to purify the fusion derivatives through a simple and cost-effective inverse transition cycling

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: abandiera@units.it (A. Bandiera).

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(ITC) method, which exploits their unique thermo-responsive nature [7]. The recombinant Human Elastin-like Polypeptide (HELP) was shown an effective carrier for AMP production [8]. Recently, to improve the performance and extend the application of this family of carriers, a new ELP biopolymer was developed, showing enhanced thermo-responsive properties and cytocompatibility with respect to HELP [9]. Nevertheless, handling this new biopolymer was not trivial due to its low transition temperature (T_t). In this work the modification of this biopolymer to employ it as a carrier for the production of bioactive AMPs is described. The aim of the study was i) to evaluate the features of this new carrier, ii) to compare its properties, as well as those of the indolicidin fusion with the already described HELP carrier and its indolicidin (HIn) derivative [8]. This approach, based on a structure-driven design, represents a novel strategy to evidence and investigate peptide sequence-related functions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Cloning, expression, and purification of the elastin-based biopolymers

The nucleotide sequence coding for the new ELP containing 4 blocks of alternating cross-linking and elastin-like domains (named UELP4, Fig. 1S) was assembled following a modification of the already described strategy [9] and employing only two duplication steps. The indolicidin domain nucleotide sequence (In, GenBank: AAB21494.1) was obtained from Eurofins Genomics and was in-frame cloned at the C-terminal region of UELP4 gene, exploiting the unique *DraIII* - *HindIII* restriction sites, as already described for the HIn polypeptide [8] and resulting in the U4In (UEL4-In) coding sequence. UELP4 and U4In coding sequences were verified by Sanger sequencing (Eurofins Genomics).

The UELP4 and U4In biopolymers developed herein, as well as the HELP and HIn biopolymers, were produced in the *E. coli* C3037I strain and purified following the already described protocols [8]. For long-term storage, the biopolymers were freeze-dried, and for biological characterization, sterilization was achieved by 0.22 μm filtration.

2.2. Physicochemical characterization

2.2.1. Turbidimetry analysis

The turbidity of biopolymer samples was measured as absorbance at $\lambda = 350$ nm in the range of 5–50 °C at a heating scan rate of 0.5 °C/min on a Jenway 6300 spectrophotometer (Hong Kong, China). Purified biopolymers were dissolved to a final concentration of 2 mg/mL in Tris/NaCl buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl at pH = 8.0, 0.15 M NaCl). The solutions were equilibrated at 4 °C for 16 h before analyses. The turbidity was compared to a calibrated zero absorbance measured on the filtered solvent as a blank. Data were fitted using a Boltzmann sigmoidal function. The temperature corresponding to 50 % of the maximum absorbance value was considered the transition temperature (T_t).

2.2.2. Circular dichroism

Biopolymers were dissolved at a concentration of 0.1 mg/mL in Tris/NaCl buffer. Circular dichroism (CD) spectra were recorded at $T = 10$ °C in a thermostatic cell from λ 200 to 500 nm on a Jasco J-710 spectrometer under constant nitrogen flux. The primary structure was evaluated using the ProtParam (ExPASy) tool available on the SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics website [10]. The grand average of hydropathy value (GRAVY) for proteins was calculated as the average of hydropathy values of all the amino acids in the sequence. The prediction of secondary structures or the biopolymers was based on the primary amino acid sequences by using GOR IV software from the ExPASy website (<https://www.expasy.org/>). The CD spectra were deconvoluted using the spectra analysis of the online program on the BestSel web server of ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Hungary, and the percentage of each secondary structure was calculated [11].

2.3. Assessment of the antibacterial properties of the elastin-based biopolymers

2.3.1. MIC and MBC assays

Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimal Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) towards two Gram-negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 8739 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 15442, and a Gram-positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* DSM 799 were used to evaluate the antibacterial activity of the biopolymers.

Bacterial MIC was determined according to ISO 20776-1:2019 guidelines [12]. Briefly, the bacteria were maintained in Mueller-Hinton agar plates (MHA, 2 g of beef extract, 17.5 g of acid hydrolysate of casein, 1.5 g starch, 17 g agar per liter). From a freshly cultured plate, one colony was inoculated into the Mueller-Hinton broth (MHB, i. e., MHA without agar) and grown overnight at 37 °C in a shaking incubator (160 rpm). The overnight culture was then diluted 1/30 in MHB and grown until OD₆₀₀ reached 0.5–0.6 units. Then, the OD₆₀₀ of the bacterial culture was adjusted to 0.025 with 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 6.5 (NaPi) and was further diluted 100 times in the same buffer. The bacteria at the concentration of $\sim 10^5$ cells/mL were deposited in a 96-well microplate and exposed to different concentrations of the biopolymers solved in NaPi buffer. Exposure for the first hour was carried out in NaPi buffer and for the following 24 h in MHB medium at 37 °C in static conditions. After the incubation, the OD₆₀₀ values were read using a BioTek Synergy microplate reader (Agilent, Santa Clara, California, USA). Bacteria cells cultured in the absence of the biopolymers were used as the positive growth control. For each biopolymer concentration, the percent of bacterial growth with respect to the average of the control was calculated, and the concentration that decreased bacterial growth by 100 % in more than half of the measurements was considered the MIC. Four replicates in triplicate were performed for each biopolymer.

MBC was determined following a protocol similar to that of MIC, but at the end of 24 h of exposure, serial dilutions were made from each microplate well. 20 μL of each serial dilution were spread onto MHA plates, and after 24 h at 37 °C, colonies were counted when their number was comprised between 3 and 30. Four replicas in triplicate were performed for each biopolymer. The concentration of biopolymer that decreased the CFU by 99 % in more than half of the measurements compared with non-treated bacteria control was considered the MBC.

2.3.2. Inhibition of biofilm formation

P. aeruginosa ATCC 15442 was used in biofilm studies following the already described methodology [13]. To assess the effect of biopolymers on biofilm formation, bacteria were pre-grown overnight in LB at 37 °C (160 rpm). The overnight culture of bacteria was diluted 1/30 and further grown in LB until OD₆₀₀ reached 0.5–0.6 units. Then, the OD₆₀₀ of bacterial culture was adjusted to 0.025 with NaPi buffer and was further diluted 100 times in NaPi buffer to reach $\sim 10^5$ cells/mL. Bacteria were then transferred to 96-well microplates and exposed to biopolymers at pre-determined concentrations in NaPi buffer for 1 h at room temperature. Then, 3.3 volumes of LB were added up to a total volume of 200 μL , and the reverse side of a 96-well non-skirted PCR plate (# 4ti-0720/C, Framestar) was inserted into the microplates and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C without shaking in wet conditions. The PCR plate wells act as pegs on which biofilm can grow. Then the PCR plate with biofilm on it was removed from the 96-well microplates and carefully extensively washed in 0.15 M NaCl. To stain the biofilm formed on the outside of PCR plate wells, 200 μL of 0.5 % crystal violet dye (5 g of crystal violet in 1 L of water, filtered before use) was added to each well of a fresh 96-well plate, and the PCR plate was placed into it (each peg in a different well) and incubated for 30 min at room temperature. Thereafter the PCR plate was extensively washed 3 times in 0.15 M NaCl and placed in a new 96-well microplate where each well was filled with 200 μL of 96 % ethanol. To better wash off the crystal violet dye, the PCR plate was tapped and gently agitated for 5 min. The resulting solutions

were diluted 5 times, and absorbance at 595 nm was measured with a BioTek Synergy microplate reader (Agilent, Santa Clara, California, USA). All measurements were conducted in two biological and four technical replicates. Minimal Biofilm Inhibition Concentration (MBIC) was defined as the lowest concentration of biopolymers that inhibited 100 % biofilm formation in more than half of the measurements.

2.3.3. Morphological evaluation by scanning electron microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to assess bacterial cell morphology. Coatings of each biopolymer were prepared on 13 mm-diameter sterile plastic coverslips (# 83.1840.002, Sarstedt, Germany). 2 mg/mL aqueous solution of UELP4, U4In, HELP, and HIn biopolymers and 50 μ L of each solution were deposited on the coverslips, which were then dried by evaporation at room temperature under the sterile hood, resulting in 100 μ g of biopolymer per cm^2 thin film coatings.

The bacterial culture was diluted to OD 0.25 (approximately 2.5×10^8 CFU/mL) in NaPi buffer. 20 μ L of this dilution were deposited onto the coated surface of the plastic coverslips and incubated for 2 h at room temperature. After the incubation, the bacterial solution was removed from each sample, which was washed twice with 50 μ L of PBS pH 7.2. Then, the samples were fixed at room temperature with 50 μ L of 2.5 % (v/v) glutaraldehyde in PBS for 30 min. After removing glutaraldehyde, the coverslips were rinsed again by soaking in PBS. Sample dehydration was performed with increasing concentrations of ethanol/water (30 %, 50 %, 70 %, 90 %, and 100 %), soaking each sample in 1 mL of solution for 5 min for each step. Subsequently, samples were dried under the hood flow and mounted on carbon tape-covered aluminum stubs. The samples were sputter-coated with chromium using a Q150T ES plus (Quorum Technologies Ltd., UK) equipment. The morphological analysis was then performed with a scanning electron microscope (Gemini 300, Zeiss, Germany) working in secondary electron detection mode. The working distance was set at about 8.5 mm to obtain the appropriate magnification, and the acceleration voltage was set at 5 kV.

2.3.4. Bacterial viability assay

To assess the viability of bacteria deposited on the coatings, a Live/Dead assay (kit #L7012, BacLight™ LIVE/DEAD™, Thermo Fischer Scientific, Massachusetts, USA) was performed following the supplier's instruction. The incubation with bacterial cells on the 100 μ g/ cm^2 biopolymer thin films was performed as detailed in the previous session (2.3.3). After the incubation, the bacterial solution was removed from each sample that was then washed twice with 50 μ L of 0.15 M NaCl, removing the liquid excess. 20 μ L of Live/Dead reagent diluted in 0.15 M NaCl were added per coverslip and incubated for 15 min. Samples were analyzed by a Leica DM4000 Upright Fluorescence Microscope equipped with a Leica DFC420 C Digital Camera for image capture. The excitation/emission maxima used were 480/500 nm (SYTO 9) and 490/635 nm (propidium iodide).

2.4. Cell culture and cytocompatibility assessment

For biological testing, primary human dermal fibroblasts of human origin (NHDF) (C-12300, PromoCell®, Heidelberg, Germany) were used. Fibroblasts were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10 % Fetal Calf Serum, 100 U/mL penicillin, and 100 μ g/mL streptomycin in standard conditions (37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5 % CO_2). The cytotoxicity of biopolymers was assessed using two different approaches: the addition of biopolymers in the cell culture medium and cell seeding directly on the biopolymer coatings.

To evaluate the effect of the presence of the biopolymers in the culture medium, NHDFs were seeded at 10^4 cells/well in tissue culture 96-well plates and incubated in standard conditions for 24 h. Then, the culture medium of each well was removed, and it was replaced with 100 μ L of serum-free medium containing the biopolymers at the desired concentrations (0.1 and 0.4 mg/mL) or 10 % DMSO (cytotoxicity

control). In addition, wells where only serum-free medium was added were used as the NHDF cell viability control. The cultures were incubated in standard conditions, and then viability and cytotoxicity were assessed after 24 h.

For direct contact testing, thin film coatings were prepared in the well bottom of the standard 96-well tissue culture plates before seeding. For each biopolymer, 30 μ L of a 0.01 μ g/ μ L aqueous solution was deposited per well and evaporated to dryness at room temperature under the sterile hood flow, resulting in a final coating containing 1 μ g of biopolymer per cm^2 . NHDF cells were seeded at 10^4 cells/well in 100 μ L of serum-free medium, and the cultures were carried on for 24 h. The NHDF culture on uncoated tissue culture polystyrene was the untreated control, while NHDF in the presence of 10 % DMSO was the cytotoxicity control [14].

2.4.1. Cell viability assay

Cell viability was assessed by the Cell Meter™ Colorimetric WST-8 Cell Quantification Kit (# 22770-AAT, Stratech, Cambridge, UK). The number of metabolically active cells was assessed by absorbance increase at 450 nm. Cells cultured in the different conditions were washed with PBS before the addition of 10 % WST-8 diluted in the culture medium. After incubation for 1 h at 37 °C, 100 μ L aliquots of the reaction mixture were transferred onto a fresh 96-well plate, and absorbance at 450 nm was measured using a Multiskan™ FC microplate reader (VWR, Radnor, Pennsylvania, USA). Viability was calculated as the percentage with respect to the untreated control.

2.4.2. Cytotoxicity assay

The lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) assay, which is based on the levels of LDH released after plasma membrane damage, was carried out using the colorimetric CyQUANT™ LDH cytotoxicity assay (# C20301, Thermo Fischer Scientific, Massachusetts, USA). The assay is based on the conversion of lactate to pyruvate via NAD^+ reduction to NADH, which is quantified following the appearance of a red formazan product that is spectrophotometrically detected at 490 nm. 50 μ L aliquots from treated and untreated cultures were transferred to a fresh 96-well plate after 24 h of exposure to the treatments, and 50 μ L of the CyQUANT™ solution was added to each well. The plate was incubated at room temperature for 30 min, protected from light, and then absorbance at 490 nm was measured using a Multiskan™ FC microplate reader (VWR, Radnor, Pennsylvania, USA). Cytotoxicity was calculated as the percentage of the cell death control after subtracting the absorbance of the untreated control.

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism 10.3.1 (464) software (Boston, USA). The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to ensure that data was normally distributed. Significances for the WST-8 cell viability and LDH release cell death assays with respect to the corresponding control were calculated using an analysis of variance (ANOVA), and pairwise comparisons were done using Dunnett's multiple comparisons test.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the elastin-based biopolymers and comparison of their physicochemical properties

HELP is a well-described recombinant biopolymer based on the repeated -VAPGVG- hexapeptidic sequence found in the exon 24 of the human elastin showing the temperature-dependent behavior that characterizes the ELPs [15]. HELP was successfully exploited as a fusion carrier for the expression of the well-studied AMP indolicidin, thus establishing a methodology to produce sequences belonging to this group of bioactive domains [8]. In Fig. 1, the primary structures of the HELP carrier and its fusion with indolicidin (HIn) are reported.

Recently, a new carrier based on the nonapeptidic repeat -VPGXGVGAG- coded by the exon 26 of the human elastin was described

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the primary structure of the HELP and UELP4 carriers and their fusion constructs with indolicidin. The cross-linking domains (green diamonds) and elastin-like domains (red in HELP and HIn; white in UELP4 and U4In) are schematized. The His-tag (solid black circle) constitutes the N-terminal sequence of all four biopolymers, whereas the indolicidin domain (purple) constitutes the C-terminal region of the antimicrobial fusion constructs. Right bottom, Coomassie blue staining of 14 % SDS-PAGE analysis of the ITC purified elastin-based biopolymers used in this study. Lane 1, HELP (solid red arrow); lane 2, HIn (open red arrow); lane 3, UELP4 (solid black arrow); and lane 4, U4In (open black arrow). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

[9]. The expression product, named UELP, showed a sharper transition and a lower T_t compared to HELP. These properties may further improve the final production yield since this last is dependent on the thermo-responsive behavior of the biopolymer. In addition, the biological evaluation of UELP revealed an unexpected capacity for promoting cell adhesion that has not been observed for HELP [9]. Thus, it was of interest to assess the performance of the new UELP biopolymer as the fusion carrier for the production of AMP domains, comparing it with the HELP carrier. However, the lower T_t of the UELP biopolymer (around 23 °C), with respect to that of HELP, made it difficult to manipulate the samples at the working temperature [9]. Moreover, the fusion with a hydrophobic domain is expected to further lower the T_t [16], resulting in phase separation even below room temperature. Therefore, considering that the T_t of the ELP depends on the chain length [17], a new biopolymer corresponding to half of the UELP macromolecule was realized and named UELP4 (Fig. 1). UELP4 is composed only of four monomers at difference of HELP, which consists of eight monomers alternating cross-linking and elastin-like domains (Fig. 1 and 1S). UELP4 showed, as expected, an increased T_t (27 °C) with respect to UELP, which made it suitable to be used as a carrier (Fig. 2). Hence, following the same strategy adopted to produce HIn [8], the U4In biopolymer derivative was realized, employing UELP4 as a carrier (Fig. 1).

All four biopolymers were produced and purified exploiting their thermo-responsive behavior (Fig. 1). The yield of UELP4 and the U4In fusion derivative was more than one-third higher (with an average of 300 mg of biopolymer per liter of bacterial culture) compared to that of the HELP counterparts (with an average of 200 mg/L), thus evidencing the advantage of the use of UELP4 as an AMP carrier. The comparison of the thermo-responsive behavior of the biopolymers showed that the fusion of the indolicidin to UELP4 had a significant effect on the T_t (Fig. 2).

In particular, the T_t difference between HELP and HIn corresponded to about 5 °C, whereas the T_t difference between of UELP4 and U4In was >10 °C (Fig. 2 and Table 2S). Keeping into account the different sizes of the two carriers, it may not be surprising that the effect of indolicidin fusion was stronger on the shortest UELP4 rather than on the HELP carrier (Fig. 1). The addition of the indolicidin domain always resulted

Fig. 2. Temperature-dependent behavior of the elastin-based biopolymers used in this study at the concentration of 2 mg/mL in 10 mM Tris/HCl pH 8 and 0.15 M NaCl. HELP (solid red line), HIn (dashed red line), UELP4 (solid black line), U4In (dashed black line). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

in a decrease in the calculated hydropathy index (H-index), as can be expected when an increase in the number of charged amino acids occurs (Table 1). However, indolicidin is composed of amino acids endowed with diametrically opposed properties, being rich in arginine and lysine as well as in the highly hydrophobic tryptophan. However, this fusion domain has a predominantly apolar surface area (Table 1S), and this gives an explanation for the drastic drop of the T_t observed for the UELP4 when fused with this domain, as already reported for other ELP fusions [16]. Turbidimetry measurements (Fig. 2) showed a T_t decrease for both the HIn and U4In fusions with respect to their carrier counterparts, indicating that the effect of the gain in hydrophobicity

Table 1

Comparison of the main physicochemical parameters and distribution of the secondary structures of the HELP and UELP4 biopolymers and of their indolicidin fusion derivatives. Total amino acid number (a.a.), H-index, as well as the percent of α -helical, β -sheet, and random coiled (rc) structures are indicated.

	H-index	a.a.	Negative charged a.a. (%)	Positive charged a.a. (%)		α (%)	β (%)	rc (%)
HELP	1.10	536	0	17	GOR IV	26	4	70
					CD	27	8	65
HIn	0.97	594	1	25	GOR IV	27	5	68
					CD	25	9	66
UEL4	0.87	268	0	9	GOR IV	25	24	51
					CD	24	22	54
U4In	0.69	326	1	17	GOR IV	26	26	48
					CD	22	29	49

prevailed. The DSC analysis substantially confirmed all the T_i values obtained by the turbidimetry analysis (Table 2S). The transition enthalpies (ΔH) and entropies (ΔS) were positive for all biopolymers, pointing to an entropy-driven process of dehydration, as previously described [15]. The ΔH decreased about six folds from 43.2 kcal/mol for the HELP carrier to 7.06 kcal/mol for the HIn fusion biopolymer and two-fold, from 9.64 kcal/mol for the UELP4 to 4.22 kcal/mol for the U4In fusion biopolymer (Table 2S). The mainly entropic nature of the inverse transition processes was also confirmed by the observed large ΔS variations (Table 2S). UELP4 showed a lower ΔS compared to HELP, indicating a lower hydrophobicity and reflecting the different molecular mass of the two carriers. Both HIn and U4In fusions showed lower ΔS compared to the respective carrier counterparts.

Overall, these results showed that, similarly to the HELP biopolymer, UELP4 was an effective carrier for producing indolicidin. Notably, the

yields of UELP4 and U4In were substantially higher compared to those of HELP and HIn biopolymers due to the improved transition properties of the UELP4 carrier with respect to HELP. Moreover, taking into account the respective molecular weight of the HELP and the UELP4 carriers, for the same biomass, the production of the bioactive domain fused to UELP4 is doubled with respect to that of the HELP derivative.

3.2. Evaluation of the antibacterial properties of the elastin-like biopolymers

Indolicidin is a well-characterized antimicrobial peptide active towards planktonic Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, and anti-biofilm activity has also been reported [18]. Therefore, in order to assess and compare the effect of the four biopolymers on bacterial cells, growth inhibition, microbicidal effects, and biofilm formation capability were

Fig. 3. Antimicrobial and antibiofilm activity of the elastin-based biopolymers. Effects of the biopolymers on the growth of (A) *S. aureus*, (B) *E. coli*, and (C) *P. aeruginosa*. (D) *P. aeruginosa* biofilm formation. The percentages of bacterial growth were calculated with respect to the untreated control and are represented as the mean \pm SD of at least four biological replicates. HELP (solid red symbol), HIn (open red symbol), UELP4 (solid black symbol), U4In (open black symbol). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

tested. The Gram-positive *S. aureus*, as well as the Gram-negative *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, were employed as model strains according to standard antibacterial testing methodologies. As expected, no detectable antimicrobial activity was observed when the microorganisms were exposed to the HELP biopolymer at any of the concentrations tested. Unexpectedly, the UELP4 carrier itself showed a significant antibacterial activity towards the Gram-negative strains tested (Fig. 3A–C and Table 2).

Except for their size, the only difference between these two carriers resides in the sequence of their elastin-like hydrophobic domains (Fig. 1S). Thus, the nonapeptidic repeat-based sequence of the UELP4 elastin-like domain may be responsible for the observed effect. Notably, the secondary structure of UELP4 significantly differed from that of HELP, mainly in the percent of β -sheet content at the expense of the random coil fraction (Table 1). Interestingly, β -sheet AMPs are described to disrupt bacterial membranes by the formation of toroidal pores [19]. In this light, the observed effect of UELP4 on Gram-negative bacteria may be related to the presence of β -structure in this biopolymer. No effect on *S. aureus* growth was observed for UELP4, which may be explained, at least in part, by the reported capacity of this strain to bind to soluble tropoelastin via specific membrane components, like the 25 kDa EbpS and the MSCRAMM proteins found in Gram-positive strains, likely involved in the bacterial colonization of elastin-rich tissues exposed to injuries [20,21]. No obvious homologs of this protein are described yet for the Gram-negative bacteria [22], suggesting a different way of interacting with the host between these two classes of microorganisms.

E. coli and *P. aeruginosa* were significantly affected by the presence of HIn and U4In, whereas *S. aureus* was the less sensitive microorganism, and only U4In slightly reduced bacterial growth of this last strain (Fig. 3A–C and Table 2). However, the U4In biopolymer was significantly more effective than HIn on the Gram-negative bacteria, with MIC and MBC values ranging from 0.17 and 0.35 μ M (Figs. 3, Tables 2 and 3S), demonstrating the powerful antimicrobial capacity of this new fusion construct. Likewise, the formation of *P. aeruginosa* biofilm was most effectively hindered by U4In with a minimal biofilm inhibitory concentration of 0.35 μ M (Figs. 3D, Tables 2 and 3S). It is likely that the intrinsic antimicrobial capacity of UELP4 synergized with that of indolicidin. Thus, depending on the carrier employed, the indolicidin fusion constructs showed different antimicrobial activity (Fig. 3 and Table 2). This difference was more explicit in the case of Gram-negative bacteria, with U4In MIC values about 10 times lower than those of HIn.

In order to qualitatively assess the effect on bacteria, *E. coli* cells were incubated on surfaces coated with the biopolymers, and the morphological changes were evaluated using SEM analysis (Fig. 4A).

In agreement with what was reported for *P. aeruginosa* in an earlier

Table 2

Minimal inhibitory (MIC), minimal bactericidal (MBC), and minimal biofilm inhibitory (MBIC) concentrations of the elastin-like biopolymers employed in this study. Values are expressed in μ M.

	MIC	MBC	MBIC
<i>S. aureus</i>			
HELP	>22	>22	n.d.
HIn	>22	>22	n.d.
UEL4	>22	>22	n.d.
U4In	>22	>22	n.d.
<i>E. coli</i>			
HELP	>22	>22	n.d.
HIn	2.8	2.8	n.d.
UEL4	2.8	2.8	n.d.
U4In	0.35	0.35	n.d.
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			
HELP	>22	>22	>22
HIn	5.5	5.5	1.40
UEL4	1.4	1.4	0.75
U4In	0.17	0.35	0.35

study [8], the *E. coli* cells deposited on HELP coating showed the typical morphology of healthy cells. At difference, on all the other thin film coatings, the bacterial cell morphology was significantly affected. Cell shape change from rod-like to spherical and membrane blebbing as well as bulges formation were observed (Fig. 4A). The presence of debris, likely due to the loss of cell integrity, was evident, especially for the U4In thin film, that showed the most powerful capacity for cell disruption, and almost no intact cells were detectable. The live/dead assay supported these observations, confirming the highest cell viability on the HELP thin film and significant viability reduction on all the other coatings (Fig. 4B). The disruption of the bacterial membranes evidenced by the SEM analysis (Fig. 4A) was consistent with the detected antimicrobial activity of the two indolicidin fusion biopolymers (Fig. 3B). It is described that stressful conditions, like the presence of indolicidin or other harmful compounds, lead to prominent morphological change of cell shape, formation of bulges and membrane blebbing in Gram-negative strains [8,23]. Unexpectedly, a very similar effect was detected for the UELP4-coated surface, where spherical corpuscles of different sizes were evident. The aspect of the cells resembled that of the bacteria in contact with both the HIn and U4In coatings rather than the bacteria in contact with the HELP coating (Fig. 4A). The presence of a significant fraction of dead cells on the UELP4 coating (Fig. 4B) as well as the radial diffusion assay (Fig. 2S) further confirmed the already observed antimicrobial capacity of UELP4 (Fig. 3). These results suggested that some regions of elastin may harbor cryptic antimicrobial activity. It is described that the fragments originating from the degradation of extracellular matrix protein often are endowed with biological activity and for this reason, they are known as matrikines [24]. In this light, the data point to the UELP4 sequence, inspired to the elastin exon 26, as another interesting example of an encrypted bioactive motif. Given that the exon 26 sequence is the most conserved in Mammals and that many bacteria can secrete elastolytic enzymes [25], the presence of a sequence endowed with antimicrobial activity in the elastin protein may be not surprising. It may represent an innate defense mechanism developed by the host. Recently, the antibacterial activity of elastin hydrolysates has been described, supporting this hypothesis [26].

3.3. Cytocompatibility assessment of the elastin-based biopolymers

The cytocompatibility of the biopolymers was assessed employing normal dermal fibroblasts of human origin (NHDF). Given the difference in the molecular weight of the biopolymers, the assays were done in the presence of the same amount of biopolymers. For this reason, cytocompatibility assays were performed in the range of 0.1–0.4 mg/mL, corresponding to concentrations of about 2 to 20 μ M, depending on the biopolymer mass. To evaluate the effect on cell metabolism and viability, two different setups were selected to expose the cells to the biopolymers.

In the first configuration, the biopolymers were dissolved in serum-free medium and were added to the cultures 24 h after cell seeding, as detailed in the Materials and methods section. The cultures were carried out for a further 24 h, and then, two assays were performed to evaluate cell proliferation and viability as well as to detect any possible cytotoxic effect. As indicated in Fig. 5A, the mean values of proliferation of NHDF cultures treated with the biopolymers at both of the concentrations tested were over the threshold of 70 %, which, according to ISO 10993-5:2009, is the limit value below which a material is considered cytotoxic [27]. These results were confirmed by the LDH assay, which is based on the lactate dehydrogenase activity released from the cytoplasm into the environment through the damaged cell membrane and establishes that materials with LDH values above 30 % are considered cytotoxic [28]. For all the biopolymers, LDH values were below 10 % (Fig. 5B).

In the second setup, the cells were seeded directly on the biopolymer-coated surfaces to evaluate the effect of their direct contact with the recombinant compounds. In Fig. 6A and B, the two assays confirmed the high viability and the absence of any significant cytotoxicity of the

Fig. 4. Morphological and viability evaluation of *E. coli* cells deposited on the elastin-based biopolymers coatings. (A) Representative SEM images of *E. coli* cells deposited on the biopolymers' thin films; the scale bar is 2 μm . (B) Representative fluorescence Live/Dead assay images of *E. coli* cells deposited on the elastin-like-based surfaces. Live bacterial cells are shown in green, while dead ones are represented in red; the bar is 20 μm . HELP (solid red box), HIn (dashed red box), UELP4 (solid black box) and U4In (dashed black box). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Cell viability and cytotoxicity evaluation of the NHDF cultures treated with the elastin-based biopolymers. (A) NHDFs viability assessed by WST-8 assay. (B) Cytotoxicity evaluated by the LDH release assay. For both assays, the effect of the biopolymers was determined 24 h after exposure. The values are represented as mean \pm SD. HELP (solid red bars), HIn (open red bars), UELP4 (solid black bars) and U4In (open black bars). The cytotoxicity threshold is indicated by the dashed black line. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Cell viability and cytotoxicity evaluation of the NHDF cultured on the surfaces coated obtained with HELP, UELP4, and their fusion derivatives. (A) NHDF cell viability assessed by WST-8 assay. (B) Cytotoxicity evaluated by the LDH release assay. For both assays, the effect of the biopolymer coating was determined 24 h after seeding. The values are represented as mean \pm SD. HELP (solid red bars), HIn (open red bars), UELP4 (solid black bars) and U4In (open black bars). The cytotoxicity threshold is indicated by the dashed black line. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

biopolymers towards NDHF cells.

Altogether, these results showed that neither the presence nor the direct contact of the biopolymers with the NHDF affected cell viability, and no cytotoxic effects were detected. However, regarding the possible applications of the biopolymers described in this study, unwanted effects on cells and organisms cannot be excluded, taking into account that elastin-derived fragments are endowed with bioactivity [29]. Despite specific receptors have not been identified yet, short sequences carrying the repeats of the elastin-like domains of both carriers have been described to exhibit chemoattractant properties as well as cell proliferative effects [30]. Thus, further investigation is necessary to evaluate the long-term effects of the biopolymers and of their degradation products on the biological systems.

4. Conclusions

The development of new tools by biotechnological techniques is one of the cutting-edge strategies to face global threats like the emergence of pandemics and the rise of antimicrobial resistance. The proposed approach is original, owing to the customizable system of the elastin-derived macromolecules with a tightly controlled primary structure. This study compared the performance of two recombinant biomimetic polypeptides as fusion carriers for AMP production. The HELP and the new UELP4 carrier, based on different amino acid sequences derived from the hydrophobic domain of elastin, as well as their respective fusions with the indolicidin model peptide, have been assessed and

characterized for their antimicrobial properties. The shortest UELP4 carrier showed improved thermo-responsive properties that were maintained after the bioactive fusion with the antimicrobial peptide, resulting in an effective way to produce these active biopolymers with improved yield. Unlike HELP, UELP4 itself showed an unexpected antimicrobial activity. Notably, the antimicrobial capacity of UELP4 was further exacerbated after the fusion of the indolicidin domain. Another prominent feature of UELP4 carrier resides in its biomimetic trait, being based on a naturally occurring conserved Mammalian sequence. The cytocompatibility and the biomimetic nature limit the likelihood of the risk of eliciting resistance and immune responses, pointing to UELP4 as one of the most suitable carriers for producing AMPs intended for clinical applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Laura Colomina-Alfaro: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Paola Sist:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Angela Ivask:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Brenda Raid:** Investigation, Data curation. **Hanna Ainelo:** Investigation, Data curation. **Abeer Shaalan:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Lucy Di Silvio:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Ranieri Urbani:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Artemis Stamboulis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding

acquisition. **Antonella Bandiera**: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

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If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.137682>.

Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this manuscript and its supplementary information files.

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